

Making Photocatalyst Screening Photo-Efficient – Geometric Radiation Field Model Assisted Design of a Direct Irradiation Module for the Multi-Batch Screening Reactor

(Supporting Information)

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1. Photonic Characterization

Table 1: Characterized LED and product numbers.

LED	Manufacturer	Product Number
365 nm	New Energy	LST1-01G01-UV01-00
530 nm	New Energy	LST1-01F06-GRN1-00

Photon Flux Calculations

The externally applied photon flux q_{ext} for narrow-banded emitters like LEDs can be calculated using a monochromatic approximation according to Eq. (1), with the radiant power P_{rad} at the peak emission wavelength λ_{peak} of the LED emitter, Planck's constant h , the speed of light c and Avogadro's number N_A .

$$q_{\text{ext}} = \frac{P_{\text{rad}} \cdot \lambda_{\text{peak}}}{N_A \cdot h \cdot c} \quad (1)$$

Radiometry

Radiometric measurements were performed using two LED types (UV 365 nm, green 530 nm) listed in Table 1. LEDs were characterized at constant electrical current at 350 mA, 500 mA, 700 mA and 1000 mA. Measured optical powers were converted to photon fluxes under the assumption of monochromatic emission at the peak emission wavelengths of the respective LEDs (UV 365 nm peak emission: 365 nm and blue 530 nm peak emission: 530 nm) ^[1,2]. For the radiometric measurements, LEDs were coupled to an integrating sphere using a 30 mm port. The integrating sphere was coupled to an Avantes Avaspec-ULS2048CL-EVO-RS 02/17 spectrometer (50 μm slit Slit-200-RS) using an Avantes FC-UVIR600-2-ME-SMA/FC fiber optic cable. Optical power calculations were based on calibration data using an Energetiq EQ-99X-FC plasma light source as reference. The results of the radiometric measurements are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Calculated optical powers and corresponding photon fluxes for the evaluated UV 365 nm and blue 530 nm LEDs.

2. Detailed Information about the Direct Irradiation Module

CAD models of the deployed heat sinks and 3D printed components are provided in the corresponding GitHub repository <https://github.com/photonZfeed/modularPhotoreactor> .

Reflector with Fixed Height

Figure 2: a Assembly of reflector with fixed height and b mounting scheme and components of direct irradiation module.

Table 2: Component list fixed-height reflector.

Nr.	Component	Reference
1	PTFE reflector support 350 mm × 100 mm (red plexi glas)	PMMA PLEXIGLAS
1a	PTFE reflector 350 mm × 100 mm	OPF200.XXX.300-U-K, BERGHOF Fluoroplastics
2	PTFE reflector support 330 mm × 100 mm (red plexi glas)	PMMA PLEXIGLAS
2a	PTFE reflector 330 mm × 100 mm	OPF200.XXX.300-U-K, BERGHOF Fluoroplastics
3	aluminum LED mounting plate 400 mm × 400 mm	Aluminum, custom made (LED_mount_400.stl × 400.stl)
4	aluminum heatsink 200 mm × 200 mm	RS PRO, 9033090 (heatsink_200.stl × 200.stl)
5	3D printed ABS reflector and heatsink holder	reflector_fixed_height_assembly.stl
5a	holder feet	holder_feet_assembly.stl
5b	corner pillar	corner_pillar_1.stl, corner_pillar_2.stl, corner_pillar_3.stl, corner_pillar_4.stl
5c	corner pillar support	corner_pillar_support.stl
5d	heatsink holder	heatsink_holder_male.stl heatsink_holder_female.stl
5e	reflector holder	reflector_holder.stl
5f	corner pillar connector	corner_pillar_connector_330mm.stl

Modular Reflector with Adjustable Height

Figure 3: Assembly of modular reflector, corresponding mounting scheme and components.

Heat sinks

Figure 4: Technical drawings of heatsink dimensions and assembly. Four 200 mm x 200 mm aluminum heatsinks (RS PRO, 903-3090) (left) and the corresponding aluminum LED mounting plate 400 mm x 400 mm with 225 LED mounting positions (right).

3. Ray Independence Studies

The stop criteria for simulations in Ansys Speos is the number of processed rays. Therefore, the precision of the results is tied to the number of rays employed in the simulation. To determine the ideal number of traced rays, a test was performed comparing the simulation time and standard deviation of the irradiance data set. Seven simulations were performed for a total of $2 \cdot 10^6$, $4 \cdot 10^6$, $8 \cdot 10^6$, $1.6 \cdot 10^7$, $3.2 \cdot 10^7$, $6.4 \cdot 10^7$, and $1.2 \cdot 10^8$ traced rays.

Figure 5 shows the standard deviation in the irradiance data set and the simulation time required by the simulations for the systems composed of 365 nm and 530 nm LEDs, respectively. Both figures show that the increase in the number of simulated rays leads to an exponential increase in the simulation time demand. The opposite happens with the standard deviation. As the number of rays increases, the deviation stabilizes at about 7 W m^{-2} and 8 W m^{-2} for the 365 nm LEDs with and without reflectors, and around 2.3 W m^{-2} and 2.7 W m^{-2} for the 530 nm LEDs with and without reflectors, respectively. Therefore, to balance the time demand with the accuracy of the results, the stop criterion of the simulations was defined as $1.6 \cdot 10^7$ rays.

Figure 5: Ray independence studies in Ansys Speos for the two investigated LED-types with- and without reflectors. $1.6 \cdot 10^7$ rays (indicated by the dotted line) were found as best trade-off between high accuracy and low runtime.

4. Irradiance and Homogeneity Calculation of Indirect Irradiation Module

The mean irradiance and homogeneity of the indirect irradiation module were determined based on the radiometric data published by Kowalczyk et al.^[3]. In that study, the optical power received on the detection plane was reported as 1.88 W for six 365 nm LEDs (type LST1-01G01-UV01-00) operated at a forward current of 500 mA, and 1.032 W for six 530 nm LEDs (type LST1-01F06-GRN1-00) operated at a current of 1 A. For the present work, the received optical power of the green LEDs was corrected by a factor of 0.5 to account for operation at 350 mA instead of 1 A, based on the current–power correlation provided by the LED manufacturer^[4].

In accordance to the reference study^[3], the radiometric data were spatially cropped to the central region of the detector plane ($16 \text{ cm} \leq x \leq 45 \text{ cm}$, $16 \text{ cm} \leq y \leq 49 \text{ cm}$). The published raw data for each LED type were normalized to the corresponding received optical power and averaged over the cropped area. This resulted in mean irradiances of 16.8 W m^{-2} for the 365 nm LEDs (500 mA) and 4.6 W m^{-2} for the 530 nm LEDs (350 mA). The corresponding homogeneities were calculated as 0.66 and 0.68, respectively, using Eq. (2) of the main manuscript.

5. Irradiance Profiles of the Investigated LED Configurations

Figure 6-Figure 13 show spatial irradiance profiles of all investigated LED configurations as obtained from the geometric radiation field model, ray tracing simulations, and radiometric measurements, both with and without the inclusion of reflectors. As the geometric radiation field model is limited to reflector-free configurations, no corresponding results are shown for arrangements including reflectors. For these cases, irradiance distributions were exclusively evaluated by ray tracing simulations and experimental radiometric measurements.

Figure 6: Irradiance profiles of the best manual configuration with- and without reflectors using eight 365 nm LEDs according to raytracing simulations and radiometric measurements.

Figure 7: Irradiance profiles of the best manual configuration with- and without reflectors using eight 530 nm LEDs according to raytracing simulations and radiometric measurements.

Figure 8: Irradiance profiles of configuration UV1 with- and without reflectors according to raytracing simulations and radiometric measurements.

Figure 9: Irradiance profiles of configuration UV2 with- and without reflectors according to raytracing simulations and radiometric measurements.

Figure 10: Irradiance profiles of configuration UV3 with- and without reflectors according to raytracing simulations and radiometric measurements.

Figure 11: Irradiance profiles of configuration GRN1 with- and without reflectors according to raytracing simulations and radiometric measurements.

Figure 12: Irradiance profiles of configuration GRN2 with- and without reflectors according to raytracing simulations and radiometric measurements.

Figure 13: Irradiance profiles of configuration GRN3 with- and without reflectors according to raytracing simulations and radiometric measurements.

6. Overview of the Candidate Sampling Routine

Number of Possible LED Arrangements and Points Classification

Without defining any restrictions, the number of possible arrangements N_{config} for placing N LEDs on N_{mount} mounting positions is given by the binomial coefficient according to Eq. (2).

$$N_{\text{config}} = \binom{N_{\text{mount}}}{N} = \frac{N_{\text{mount}}!}{N! (N_{\text{mount}}! - N!)} \quad (2)$$

For the direct irradiation module with $N_{\text{mount}} = 169$ mounting positions and $N = 8$ LEDs, this results in $1.395 \cdot 10^{13}$ possibilities. Extending the design space to variable LED numbers $1 \leq N \leq 16$ and LED heights at $N_z = 11$ discrete positions between 5 and 15 cm, Eq. (3) gives $1.24 \cdot 10^{23}$ potential candidates.

$$N_{\text{config}} = \sum_{n=1}^{N=16} \binom{N_{\text{mount}}}{n} \cdot N_z \quad (3)$$

Clearly, exhaustive screening of this design space is computationally infeasible. However, the vast majority of these configurations are not practically relevant for the design of the direct irradiation module, since homogeneous irradiation can only be achieved by homogeneous light source distribution. Therefore, two physically motivated constraints were imposed to restrict candidate generation to plausible LED arrangements.

First, point symmetry with respect to the module center was enforced, such that for every LED at position (x, y) , a corresponding LED exists at $(-x, -y)$.

Second, an equal LED contribution per Cartesian quadrant was required. For this purpose, a quadrant weight w_{Q1-4} was defined for each quadrant $Q_1 - Q_4$. Each LED contributes a weight of 1 if fully located within a quadrant, 0.5 if located on a shared axis between two quadrants, and 0.25 if positioned at the center $(0, 0)$. A quadrant weight of $N/4$ must be satisfied for $Q_1 - Q_4$, as illustrated by Eq. (4).

$$w_{Q1} = w_{Q2} = w_{Q3} = w_{Q4} = \frac{N}{4} \quad (4)$$

To efficiently navigate through the configurations that fulfill the constraints, a combinatorial decomposition strategy was employed. All viable LED configurations are represented by three integer parameters a , b , and c for a given number of LEDs. a represents the number of Q_1Q_3 -pairs, b the number of Q_2Q_4 -pairs, and c the number of symmetric axis-pairs on the x - or y -axis.

The total LED count is given by Eq. (6). $\delta_{\text{center}} = 1$ if a LED is placed at the center $(0, 0)$, and 0 otherwise. Hence, $\delta_{\text{center}} = 1$ for odd N and 0 for even N .

$$N = 2(a + b + c) + \delta_{\text{center}} \quad (5)$$

To fulfill the quadrant weight constraint Eq. (4), the parameters a , b , and c must satisfy the system of Eqs. (6)-(8) which is used to derive all feasible parameter sets (a_i, b_i, c_i) .

$$a_i + 0.5c_i + 0.25\delta_{\text{center}} = \frac{N}{4} \quad (6)$$

$$b_i + 0.5c_i + 0.25\delta_{\text{center}} = \frac{N}{4} \quad (7)$$

$$a_i + b_i + c_i = \left\lfloor \frac{N}{2} \right\rfloor \quad (8)$$

For a given LED count N , the number of possible configurations is obtained by summing the valid LED arrangements for all feasible parameter sets (a_i, b_i, c_i) according to Eq. (9). $N_{Q_1Q_3}$ and $N_{Q_2Q_4}$ represent the total number of Q_1Q_3 - and Q_2Q_4 -pairs, respectively. N_{ax} is the total number of symmetric axis-pairs on the x - or y -axis.

$$N_{\text{config}} = \sum_i \binom{N_{Q_1Q_3}}{a_i} \cdot \binom{N_{Q_2Q_4}}{b_i} \cdot \binom{N_{\text{ax}}}{c_i} \quad (9)$$

For $N = 8$, Eqs. (6)-(8) yield three valid parameter sets: $(a_1, b_1, c_1) = (2, 2, 0)$, $(a_2, b_2, c_2) = (1, 1, 2)$, and $(a_3, b_3, c_3) = (0, 0, 4)$. For the presented module, where $N_{Q_1Q_3} = N_{Q_2Q_4} = 36$ and $N_{\text{ax}} = 12$, evaluating Eq. (9) with these three parameters sets results in a total of 482,931 feasible configurations.

Configuration Sampling Approaches

Two complementary sampling strategies were implemented: a systematic brute-force sampler and a stochastic Monte Carlo sampler. In both cases, all feasible parameter combinations (a_i, b_i, c_i) were precomputed for each LED count.

The systematic sampler exhaustively generates all combinatorically possible configurations for a given N at a user-defined height. The Monte Carlo sampler was designed to statistically probe the entire design space and supports two distinct sampling modes:

1. Uniform LED sampling, where each LED count is selected with equal probability.
2. Configuration-weighted sampling, in which the probability of selecting an LED count is proportional to its estimated number of feasible configurations. This makes the probability of generating all LED arrangements independent of the LED count the same.

The LED height was treated as an independent discrete parameter from a discrete set of predefined values with uniform probability. Full random seed control was implemented to ensure reproducibility. For this study, an arbitrary seed of 42 and uniform LED-count sampling were employed to generate the 5 million Monte-Carlo sampled configurations.

It should be noted that uniform LED-count sampling inherently favors smaller LED numbers, as a larger fraction of the corresponding design space is covered compared to higher LED counts. This bias was intentionally introduced, as configurations with less LEDs are easier to handle in practice.

7. Comparison of Mean Irradiance and Homogeneity with and without Reflectors using 530 nm LEDs

Figure 14 compares the mean irradiance and irradiation homogeneity of configurations GRN1, GRN2, and GRN3 without and with reflectors, as obtained from the geometric model, ray tracing simulations, and radiometric measurements. Overall, the qualitative trends observed for the 530 nm LEDs closely align with those reported for the 365 nm LEDs and discussed in the main manuscript.

The inclusion of reflectors increased the mean irradiance by 8 % - 18 % across the investigated configurations while maintaining homogeneity values comparable to those of the reflector-free module. Upon addition of reflectors, the mean irradiance increased from configuration GRN1 to GRN3, whereas the corresponding decrease in homogeneity followed the same trend as for the reflector-free module but less pronounced.

For the reflector-free configurations, deviations between the geometric model and radiometric measurements remained below 10 % for the mean irradiance and below 7 % for homogeneity across configurations GRN1 to GRN3. For both reflector-free and reflector-

Figure 14: Comparison of the mean irradiance and homogeneity of configurations GRN1, GRN2, and GRN3 using 530 nm LEDs without and with reflectors according to the geometric model, raytracing simulations, and radiometric measurements.

supported configurations, ray tracing simulations predicted the mean irradiance with deviations below 19 % and the homogeneity with deviations below 9 % relative to experimental measurements.

8. Sources

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